

Initiation of DNA Replication and Cancer

Manuel S. Valenzuela^{1*}

¹ Department of Biochemistry and Cancer Biology, School of Medicine, Meharry Medical College, 1005 D. B. Todd Jr. Boulevard, Nashville, TN 37208

* Corresponding author, Email: mvalenzuela@mmc.edu

Abstract

DNA replication, the key determinant of cell proliferation, is a highly regulated process whose objective is to ensure that the genetic information encoded in the chromosomes is faithfully transmitted from parental to progeny cells. Failure in this regulation could lead to abnormal proliferation and genomic instability, the hallmarks of cancer cells. The initiation step in DNA replication constitutes the main target in the alteration of cell proliferation. Initiation of DNA replication requires the activation of thousands of origins of DNA replication (ORIs) which fire only once, in a pre-determined temporal order. In this review we summarize the salient features of this process, and present experimental evidence indicating that carcinogenesis and/or genomic instability may arise by a failure in the regulation of the initiation step of DNA replication.

Replication of the human genome is a highly orchestrated process that aims to duplicate the entire parental DNA only once, per cell cycle. Failure to replicate, or over-replication of any DNA region could cause the genomic alterations commonly seen in most cancers. The replication process can be divided into three stages: initiation, elongation, and termination. Of these, the initiation stage is the determinant factor for DNA duplication, and the primary target in the regulation of the entire process. Thus, it is not surprising that mutations in many of the steps in the initiation stage have been found to be associated with several cancer types. In this brief review we will first present the salient features of the initiation of DNA replication, followed by experimental evidence suggesting its relationship to tumorigenesis.

Initiation of DNA replication occurs through the activation of thousands independent units of DNA replication (replicons), which are distributed along each one of the chromosomes. Each replicon contains an origin of replication (ORI), which is recognized by a multiprotein complex that loads a helicase onto the DNA to facilitate its opening, a required step prior to DNA synthesis. ORI activation occurs in a temporarily controlled manner which is specific for each cell type, and in general it correlates with its pattern of gene expression, such that expressed genes are replicated early, whereas silent genes are replicated late, in the S phase. Although a great deal has been learned about the manner a helicase is loaded onto an ORI containing DNA and its subsequent activation, we do not yet have a clear understanding about how the temporal order of activation is established, nor how ORIs are chosen.

Figure 1

The replicon model proposed nearly 50 years ago to explain how DNA replication initiates in prokaryotes [1] has served as a good paradigm to study this stage in eukaryotes. As illustrated in Figure 1, ORI selection occurs after mitosis through the initial binding of a six-subunit complex named the origin recognition complex (ORC) which serves as a landing platform for the binding of Cdt1 and Cdc6, which load an inactive MCM2-7 onto the ORI site, to form altogether the pre-replicative complex (pre-RC). At this stage, the ORI site is said to be licensed for replication and detachment of Cdc6, Cdt1, or ORC does not remove MCM2-7 from ORI or affect

its potential helicase function. Upon entry into the S phase of the cell cycle, the action of specific S-phase cyclin-dependent kinases (CDK) and the Cdc7\ASK kinase, promote the additional recruitment of the GINS complex and Cdc45 to form the pre-initiation complex (pre-IC), as well as, the phosphorylation of several component of this complex. Phosphorylation by these kinases results in the activation of the MCM2-7 into a functional helicase, as well as the removal or inactivation of ORC, Cdc6 and free Cdt1 to prevent re-licensing, thus licensing at any given ORI occurs only once per cell cycle. Upon MCM2-7 activation and subsequent opening of the DNA strands, two forks are generated upon each of which the replisome machinery is assembled. The temporal separation of ORI licensing and firing generates a window of opportunity for the regulation of this stage: DNA synthesis does not start until all ORIs have been converted into pre-RCs, and conversely formation of pre-RCs is inhibited during the DNA synthesis phase of the cell cycle. By this simple mechanism, under-replication or over-replication of the genome is prevented.

It is reasonable to assume that the abnormal proliferation observed in cancer cells could be tied to an inappropriate expression of pre-RC proteins. Indeed in a wide variety of pre-malignant dysplasias and cancers, an increased expression of Mcm2-7 proteins has been reported [2-6]. Although the molecular basis for this increase is not well understood, MCM proteins are currently utilized as effective prognostic and diagnostic markers of abnormal cell proliferation [2,3,4,7]. Over-expression or stabilization of Cdt1 or Cdc6 leads to the development of tumors [8-11] therefore both Cdt1 and Cdc6 are classified as oncogenes. However, mutations in these genes are not commonly observed in cancers, owing perhaps to the potential lethality of such mutations. It has been proposed that limited over-replication could perhaps lead to genomic instability while being compatible with cell survival. This might be the mechanism by which several oncogenes induce tumorigenesis [12]. For example, over expression of a mutant form of cyclin D₁, an oncogene that is frequently mutated in human tumors, has been shown to lead to re-replication in a single cell cycle, which appears to be caused by the inappropriate stabilization of Cdt1 in the S phase [13]. Under this scenario, re-replicated regions could cause the formation of double strand breaks which in turn elicit the activation of the Damaged DNA Response (DDR) machinery. Mutations in the DDR system could then lead to the genetic instability observed in most cancers.

Reduced expression of some pre-RC components have also been observed to cause genetic instability and cancer but only under genotoxic conditions [14,15]. Interestingly, even though one would expect that all proliferating tissues would be equally affected by a reduced expression in these genes, each one of the two hypomorphic mutations in mice that have so far been studied, showed a particular tissue tropism. In a hypomorphic mutant

of Mcm4 (Chaos3 mutant) about 80% of the Chaos3 female mice develop mammary carcinomas [14]. In contrast, a similar mutation in Mcm2 has been reported to lead to the development of T and B-lymphomas [15]. These studies suggest that under normal conditions cells have an ample supply of MCMs to ensure the replication of the genome. Under conditions of replication stress some unlicensed ORIs may inappropriately enter the S phase, thus causing under-replication of regions of the genome. However, other tissue-specific factors may determine the observed tissue tropism in these mutants.

It has been well documented that licensed ORIs follow an established temporal pattern of activation as cells transition into the S-phase. This pattern is predetermined at the G1 phase and it varies depending on cell type and developmental stage. Some ORIs fire early, others at mid S-phase, and others much later. A correlation appears to exist between replication timing and nuclear structure. A coordinated activation of ORIs leads to the formation of replication foci, which occupy distinct nuclear territories depending on their timing of activation. Each of these foci contains hundreds of ORIs which are simultaneously activated in "replication factories". Although the nature of these "replication factories" is unknown, a nucleoprotein structure that resists high salt extraction (named the nuclear matrix, NM) has been implicated as the basic component for these factories. In agreement with this notion NM preparations have been found to be enriched for newly synthesized DNA [16-18]. More importantly, changes in both nuclear localization and NM composition have been correlated to changes in replication timing. At the gene level, gene expression has been associated with replication timing. In general, housekeeping genes replicate at early stages of the S-phase, whereas the gene expression specificity of tissues determines the timing of replication of each gene. Thus, for a given tissue, expressed genes are replicated early and repressed genes late, indicating that cellular development plays an important role in determining the temporal order of replication.

Since replication timing is associated with gene expression, a change in the replication of an early ORI into a late one could cause a disturbance in the temporal expression of crucial genes. For example, oncogenes that are normally repressed and replicate late, could be inappropriately replicated early, and cause cell transformation. Alternatively, ORIs may not efficiently function at their allotted time leaving tracts of unreplicated DNA, a potential source of genetic instability. Finally, the nuclear framework that participates in ORI firing may change, leading to an alteration in the temporal regulation of this process. Several of these changes have been observed in cancer cells.

Although it is not clear the advantage that a tight replication program offers to the cells, alterations in replication timing have been observed in blood cancers. It is also known that the temporal

order of chromosome replication influences somatic mutations rates and cancer-related somatic copy numbers alterations. In addition, changes in nuclear architecture and morphology have also been recognized as a common feature of cancer cells (reviewed in Zink et al, 2004, [19]). Finally, changes in NM composition have been reported in cancer cells and some of these changes have been utilized as the basis for diagnostic tests [19-22]. Based on these findings, it has been proposed that the structural constraints to DNA replication and transcription caused by chromatin attachment to the NM, fix the cellular developmental program. According to this model, these constraints are lifted in cancer cells, such that now these cells adopt a less specific, embryonic-like chromatin organization [23]. Chromosomal abnormalities common in cancer caused by the lack of activation of late origins have been demonstrated by studying DNA replication around chromosomal fragile sites. A single DNA fiber analysis of DNA replication around FRA3B, the most active common fragile site found in human lymphoblasts showed that the fragility of this site was dependent of tissue context. In lymphoblastoid cells and under conditions of replicative stress, few late origins surrounding the fragile site fired, thus determining the fragility of this site. In contrast, in fibroblastoid cells subjected to the same conditions, the lack of fragility of this site correlated with activity of late origins around the fragile region [24].

The human genome harbors thousands of ORIs, all of which are supposed to be licensed. It is estimated that there is at least an excess of 5 times the number of ORIs required for the complete duplication of the genome. Accordingly, ORIs have been classified into three main subgroups: Constitutive, that fire in all cell types; Flexible, that fire in some but not all cells of the same type; and Dormant, that fire only under conditions of replicative stress. It is believed that the existence of a large supply of licensed ORI offers the cell with some flexibility to adapt to metabolic changes and to ensure that the genome is fully replicated during the duration of the S phase. Several studies have suggested that the replication program changes in cancer cells, leading to an increase in the activity of ORIs [25-33]. Unfortunately, many of these reports have been limited in scope, thus support for this hypothesis is still lacking. The advent of genome wide techniques to map the position of ORIs should facilitate to settle this issue.

In summary, the study of the initiation of DNA replication has opened new vistas toward our understanding of the manner mitogens and/or mutational events may create the conditions for the abnormal proliferation and genetic instability observed in cancer cells. Alterations in the manner the licensing step is regulated, changes in the temporal order of licensed ORIs, or the specific replicative pattern adopted by the cell, may be crucial determinants in the process of carcinogenesis. Genome wide studies of all of these steps, coupled to a better understanding about the underlined

nuclear structure that facilitates and regulates these processes, are needed to obtain a complete picture of the relationship between chromosome structure and function in both normal and tumor cells.

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